

HISTORY OF THE "BOLSHEVIKS REVOLUTION" OF 1917 AND ITS IMPACT ON THE TURKESTAN REGION

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Annotatsiya: Turkiston – jahon sivilizatsiyasining qadimiy o'choqlaridan biri sifatida yuksalgan bo'lsa, XX asr boshlariga kelib Rossiya imperiyasining periferiyadagi, koloniyalashgan o'lkalaridan biri bo'lgan. Bu hudud Turkiston general-gubernatorligi ostida edi. XX asr boshidan boshlab, Turkiston uchun muhim o'zgarishlar davri boshlandi. Ushbu maqolada 1917-yilda sodir bo'lgan bolsheviklar inqilobi va uning Turkiston o'lkasiga qilgan ta'siriga oid ma'lumotlar tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Turkiston, bolsheviklar, inqilob, qurultoy, jadidchilik, SSSR.

Аннотация: Туркестан, некогда один из древнейших очагов мировой цивилизации, к началу XX века был одной из периферийных, колонизированных стран Российской империи. Эта территория входила в состав Туркестанской губернии. С начала XX века для Туркестана наступает период важных перемен. В статье анализируются сведения о большевистской революции 1917 года и ее влиянии на Туркестанский край.

Ключевые слова: Туркестан, большевики, революция, съезд, джадидизм, СССР.

Abstract: Turkestan, once one of the ancient centers of world civilization, by the beginning of the 20th century was one of the peripheral, colonized countries of the Russian Empire. This territory was under the Turkestan Governorate. Since the beginning of the 20th century, a period of important changes has begun for Turkestan. This article analyzes the information about the Bolshevik Revolution of 1917 and its impact on the Turkestan region.

Key words: Turkestan, Bolsheviks, revolution, congress, Jadidism, USSR.

INTRODUCTION. The analysis of the social life of the country's population allowed for a deeper understanding of this process, and the results were not limited. In this analysis, along with internal and external factors, the influence of natural factors was also seen. At that time, one of the main problems in Turkestan society

was the low social status of the population. During the period of economic expansion of Russian capitalism, new economic directions emerged in Turkestan: food processing, cotton ginning, railway construction, mineral extraction, and other industries began to become an integral part of the country's national economic system. However, their impact on economic and social life was significant. These industries, first of all, depended on the needs of the industrial centers of the Russian Empire, and the task of the economy in Turkestan was to supply raw materials, rather than finished products. Secondly, the one-sided development of capitalist production reduced the traditional areas of production. Local crafts could not compete with Russian products. In the country, the decline of grain fields, the decline of crafts, as a raw material base for the Russian economy, increased the country's economic dependence.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS and METHODOLOGY. On February 27, 1917, the democratic revolution in Petrograd triumphed, and the Russian Emperor Nicholas II was overthrown. With the abdication of the Russian Emperor in February 1917, the revolutionary movement entered a new phase. A provisional government was formed, but it also failed to find a solution to pressing problems such as ending the war, resolving the agrarian question, and recognizing nationalities. In this situation, the Bolsheviks, namely the Russian Social Democratic Labor Party (Bolsheviks) led by Vladimir Lenin, were able to attract a large social stratum with the slogans "Peace to the peoples, land to the peasants, factories to the workers." Finally, in October 1917, the Bolsheviks seized power. This revolution also had an impact on Turkestan. In particular, on the initiative of the young Turkestan intellectuals and religious figures, political parties such as the "Islamic Council" in March 1917, the "Shoroi Ulama" in June 1917, the "Turkish People's Center" ("Turkish Federalist Party") in July 1917, and the "Muslim Union" in September 1917 were established. [1]

On April 7, 1917, by a decree of the Provisional Government in Petrograd, N.N. The Turkestan Committee of the Provisional Government was formed under the chairmanship of Shchepkin. However, the I and II Congresses of All-Turkistan Muslims, held in April and September 1917, put forward the idea of creating the Turkestan Autonomy and opposed the transfer of power to the Soviets of Workers', Soldiers' and Peasants' Deputies. This event also directly affected Turkestan. It should be noted that Turkestan was one of the colonial territories of the Russian Empire, and the local peoples were deprived of political rights, economically backward, and culturally oppressed. After the February Revolution of 1917, political freedom expanded in Turkestan. Local intellectuals, especially representatives of the Jadid movement, took advantage of the new political conditions and began to

advance their ideas. Dreams of self-government, achieving national autonomy, reforming education and the judiciary, and ending Russian colonialism are growing among the Muslims of Turkestan.

The protection of national interests and the development of political programs remained the main issues at various congresses - Muslim congresses convened during 1917. The February Revolution played an important role in the political awakening of the Muslim population of Turkestan and the emergence of new forces that sought to lead democratic changes on the political scene. The Jadids formed the basis of the emerging national-democratic forces. They linked the ideas of development and independence of the peoples of the region with the slogans of the February Revolution and began to implement the declared principles. The organization "Shoroi Islam" (March 14, 1917) was created in Tashkent, and most of the progressives of Turkestan united around it. The Soviet of Workers' Deputies was also created in Tashkent (March 2, 1917). The Governor-General of the Turkestan region and the commander of the Turkestan Military District, General Kuropatkin, his assistant General Yerofeyev, and the chief of the district staff, General Sivere, were dismissed from their posts and sent home on March 31. [2]

On August 7, 1917, the Provisional Government established the Turkestan Committee (chairman - cadet N.N. Shchepkin), consisting of 9 people, to govern the Turkestan region. At the First Congress of All-Turkistan Muslims (April 17-21, 1917), the Central Council of Muslims of Turkestan (Kraymussovet) was established, which united all national societies, organizations, and unions. The intensification of the political crisis in the fall of 1917, changes in the balance of power in the country, created favorable conditions for the transfer of power to the Soviets, as a result of which the Bolsheviks, led by V.I. Lenin, came to power. The Bolshevization of the Petrograd and Moscow Soviets gave V.I. Lenin the reason to write his two letters to the Petrograd and Moscow Central Committees of the RSDLP(b)P ("The Bolsheviks Must Seize Power", "Marxism and Rebellion"). In these letters, written on September 12-14, 1917, V.I. Lenin put forward the task of preparing an armed uprising to overthrow the Provisional Government and establish the dictatorship of the proletariat through the soviets. "The Bolsheviks, who have achieved superiority in the Soviets of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies of the two capitals, must seize power," he wrote.

In both capitals, the revolutionary part of the people was more active, and therefore they too would lead the masses to the end, defeat their opponents, seize power and retain it. The Shoroi Ulamo, a group of religious scholars, split from the Shoroi Islamiya led by Munavvar Qori in June 1917. The Shoroi Ulamo community

was strongly opposed to any attempts by democratic national intellectuals and Muslim clerics to reform society and to the introduction of European culture. They also rejected the ideas of reforms in the educational and political spheres. The Tashkent Soviet of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies tried to skillfully use the division among the Muslims. As a result of the September events, the Tashkent Soviet sought to seize power.

On September 10, 1917, the II Congress of All Turkestan Muslims opened in Tashkent. At this meeting, a sharp opposition was expressed to the transfer of power to the Soviets of Soldiers', Workers' and Peasants' Deputies. The events of the September months further intensified political contradictions in society and separated the paths of the workers' movement and the national movement within the country. On September 17-20, 1917, at a congress of Turkestan and Kazakh Muslims in Tashkent, it was decided to establish a political party called "Ittifoqi Muslimin" common to all of Turkestan and Kazakhstan, by uniting organizations such as "Sho'roi Islamiya", "Sho'roi Ulama", and "Turon". The main issue of this congress of the "Ulamochilar" was the future political leadership of the Turkestan region, where the idea of creating a territorial federation within democratic Russia - the "Federal Republic of Turkestan" was put forward. Under the influence of the February Revolution, trade unions were organized on a large scale in Turkestan, and newspapers and magazines began to be published in the languages of the local peoples. [3]

The October Revolution of 1917 was a socio-political revolutionary movement that swept across all territories of the Russian Empire. This revolution caused serious political changes not only in the European part of Russia, but also in distant colonial territories, in particular, in the Turkestan region. The process of establishing Soviet power directly affected the life, political system, economic and cultural development of the peoples of Turkestan. On October 24–26, 1917 (November 6–8 according to the new calendar), the Bolsheviks achieved a coup d'état in Russia, overthrowing the Provisional Government. This revolution was carried out by the Russian Social Democratic Workers' Party (Bolsheviks) under the leadership of Vladimir Lenin. As a result of the revolution, Soviet power was established, and the people began to be mobilized under the slogans of Land, Peace, and Bread. Despite the fact that the Bolsheviks were supported by the majority of the city's population, they also had many internal and external enemies who did not recognize their government. A bloody civil war began in Russia.

In it, the Bolsheviks (Reds) fought against their enemies. Their opponents included the independence movements of other nations, anti-Bolshevik socialist

parties, anarchists, monarchists, and liberals. The monarchists and liberals were led by right-wing officers of the Russian Empire and supported the White movement, which aimed to restore the old imperial order. In response, the Bolshevik commissar Leon Trotsky formed the Red Army from loyal workers' militia. Although the main events took place in Moscow and Petrograd, unrest swept through almost all the cities of the empire, as well as in the regions inhabited by national minorities and rural areas. In the villages, peasants redistributed their land among themselves. [4]

The Turkestan region, which included present-day Uzbekistan, southern Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkmenistan, was part of the Russian Empire at the time of the revolution. The national and political activity of the local population increased here. The uprising of 1916 further intensified discontent in this region. As a result of the February Revolution of 1917, the Provisional Government abolished the old governor-general's rule in Turkestan, and the activity of various political forces in the country increased. Starting in November 1917, the Bolsheviks sought to seize power throughout the empire. This process was complicated in Turkestan [. "Turkestan Province Newspaper" (late 1917).]. The Bolsheviks had a strong influence among the Russian garrison and workers in Tashkent. On November 1-3, 1917, Soviet power was proclaimed in Tashkent. However, this government relied mainly on the Russian population and military forces, and remained alienated from the local Muslim population. Turkestan Muslim intellectuals and representatives of the national movement, including the Jadids, viewed the rule of the Bolsheviks with caution. They were supporters of local self-government, cultural and educational freedom.

In the national outlying regions of the Russian Empire, including Turkestan and Kazakhstan, the Soviets of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies, primarily composed of representatives of the Slavic people, Russians, resolutely carried out the process of Bolshevization. On September 12-17, 1917, in the city of Tashkent, the center of the Turkestan province, city workers and soldiers held revolutionary demonstrations, and the Tashkent Council of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies made a decision to seize power. Although the September uprisings in Tashkent did not lead to the establishment of Soviet power in Turkestan, they showed that the influence of the Bolsheviks among the people was growing. The revolutionary uprisings in Tashkent caused a great resonance throughout the country, as well as in Kazakhstan, especially in its southwestern regions - Perovsk, Kozaly, Turkestan, Chernyaev, Aulata districts. In December 1917, at the Congress of Muslims of All Turkestan held in Kokand, the Turkestan Autonomy was proclaimed. [5]

This action was not recognized by the Bolsheviks, and in February 1918 the Kokand Autonomous Oblast was liquidated by force of arms by the Red Army. One of the first decisions of the Soviet government was land reform. However, it was not fully implemented in the conditions of Turkestan. Most peasants did not correctly understand the goals of the Bolsheviks. Large landowners and the clergy openly opposed it.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION. The Soviets tried to centralize economic life, but this only increased economic inequality. After the February Revolution, the Provisional Government's indifference to the demands of workers and peasants, its slowness in resolving national issues, and Russia's participation in the war led to a nationwide crisis, creating conditions for the strengthening of extremist (far-left) parties in the center and nationalist parties on the outskirts of the country. The most active movement was carried out by the Bolsheviks. They announced that a socialist revolution would begin in Russia, which would be the beginning of a world revolution. In late August and early September 1917, the Bolsheviks, having gained a majority in the Petrograd and Moscow Soviets, began preparing for an armed coup. At a time when the peoples of Turkestan, their socio-political organizations and national leaders were striving for freedom and independence in the country, the establishment of a national state in the form of an autonomous republic within democratic Russia, and at the same time were trying to achieve all of this by peaceful means, the Bolsheviks of Turkestan, in pursuit of their own interests, were suffering from economic and food problems that had arisen due to war and economic devastation. took advantage of this and actively tried to seize power. [6]

By the fall of 1917, the state and analysis of the political forces in the country showed that the Bolsheviks were not supported by the majority of the population, and they did not have any broader social base (mainly among the local population). The population relied on the national organizations that emerged at that time, primarily the "Ulama" and "Sho'roi Islam". This was confirmed by the fact that in the elections to the city councils held in the late autumn months of 1917, the majority of votes were cast for candidates of these national parties, while the Bolsheviks received very few votes. In many cities, the Bolsheviks did not even register their candidates, because they knew that they would not be able to become members of the city дума anyway. At that time, the number of Bolsheviks in Turkestan did not exceed a few hundred, and there were almost no representatives of the local population among them. Nevertheless, the Bolsheviks in the country, taking advantage of the growing influence of their party in Russia, attempted to seize power. At the end of November 1917, Lenin, the leader of the Bolsheviks, openly

declared at the First All-Russian Congress of Soviets that his party was ready to seize all power in the country.

On November 26, 1917, the VI Congress of the Bolshevik Party, held in Petrograd on September 3, decided to seize power by armed uprising. The Bolsheviks from Tashkent, acting on the instructions of this party, on September 12, 1917, at a large rally attended by workers and soldiers, put forward a resolution drawn up in the spirit of the decisions of the VI Congress. The resolution stated the need to transfer power to the Soviets, the need to establish a Provisional Revolutionary Committee, the nationalization of industry and banks, the transfer of peasant lands to peasants, the establishment of control over production, the need to quickly confiscate food reserves from capitalists, boyars, and kulaks, and other issues.

After the February Revolution, the Provisional Government's indifference to the demands of the workers and peasants, its sluggishness and indecisiveness in resolving national issues, and Russia's continued involvement in the war led to a general crisis, which resulted in the strengthening of extremist parties in the center and nationalist parties in the peripheral regions. The Bolsheviks were the most active. They shouted that they would start a socialist revolution in Russia, that this would be the beginning of a world revolution. In late August and early September 1917, the Bolsheviks gained a majority in the Petrograd and Moscow Soviets and began preparing for an armed coup. In the fall of 1917, there were no objective conditions for the transfer of power to the Soviets in Turkestan, and the Bolsheviks had little influence among the people. The main political forces here were the Socialist-Revolutionaries and national parties.

However, when the news of the October Revolution reached Tashkent on October 27, the Bolsheviks and Left Socialist-Revolutionaries began a struggle to seize power by force. After four days of fighting, Soviet power was established in the new part of Tashkent (November 1, 1917). The Turkestan Committee of the Provisional Government was overthrown. However, the local population was almost completely absent from the armed clashes. The October Revolution had enormous consequences for Russia and the world in the 20th century. It brought about unprecedented changes in the world political order. In order to preserve the October Revolution, the Bolsheviks established a dictatorship, that is, a military-political regime that controlled all socio-political processes, that is, a regime that provided personal power. This regime implemented a policy of repression in the territory of the former USSR. Although the October Revolution was carried out under the

socialist ideals that emerged in the 18th and 19th centuries, the real goal was to seize power by any means. [7]

The October Revolution, which took place in such a historical environment, caused sharp political conflicts in Turkestan. After the Bolsheviks seized power, they tried to impose their political program on all regions, including Turkestan, and came into conflict with local national forces. The population of Turkestan, especially the Fergana Valley, Khiva, and Bukhara, viewed the Bolshevik policies with caution. Because the Bolsheviks had a strong position against religious values, the property class, and traditional social structures. This aroused sharp discontent in a society formed on the basis of centuries-old Islamic traditions. After the October Revolution, the Bolsheviks consistently continued their previous imperialist policy. In the second half of the 20th century, they expanded the borders of the empire to Western Europe. The process of the world's division into two poles began. This process continued until the 80s of the 20th century. The October Revolution radically changed the historical development of mankind.

Private property, entrepreneurship, trade, free movement, as well as freedom of thought, which ensured the development of society, were first established, and then completely banned. All things created by mankind and given by nature were turned into state property. The values of the peoples of the former Soviet Union began to gradually disappear. Artificial values such as "one people", "one family", "one language" were forcibly introduced. The revolutions of 1917 caused serious damage to the economic life of Turkestan. During the February Revolution, the system of financial and product supply from Central Russia ceased. As a result, cotton exports, railway transportation, and food supplies ceased. The disruptions in the railways led to hunger and poverty among the population. [8]

In addition, the economic policy in the country served the interests of Russian capitalists: a large part of the land was given to European nomads, cotton growing and raw material production were developed as the main industries. The local population was used as cheap labor in the agricultural sector. During the Soviet era, collectivization began under the guise of "socialization of the national economy", which led to the dispossession of peasants and economic instability. After the October Revolution, when the Bolsheviks came to power, the agricultural sector in Turkestan experienced a sharp stagnation in the process of Sovietization. Local crafts, market and trade activities declined. In particular, in the early years of Soviet economic policy, the implementation of "military communism" measures further undermined the economy of Turkestan.

After the February Revolution, social movements became active in Turkestan. Political consciousness and a sense of national identity were growing among the local population. Schools, madrasas, newspapers and magazines organized by the Jadids accelerated this process. Movements for unity and independence based on Islam flourished among the population. However, since the October Revolution, the latest Soviet policy has been directed against religious institutions and local social structures. Mosques have been closed, religious schools have been abolished, and scholars have been persecuted. This has led to sharp social discontent in society. The Soviet campaigns against the Khanates of Bukhara and Khiva, which began in 1918, as well as the abolition of Turkestan autonomy, intensified discontent and resistance movements among the population (for example, the National Liberation Movement). The slogans of equality and democracy promoted by the Soviets were not reflected in real life: the population remained completely dependent on the Russian center politically, economically, and culturally.

The February and October revolutions disrupted socio-economic life in Turkestan. Railways, industrial enterprises, and postal and communication systems were destroyed. Food shortages began in the villages. This situation further increased the distrust of the population towards Soviet power. Starting in 1918, armed resistance to Soviet power - the Press Movement - began in various regions of Turkestan, which took on the guise of a national liberation struggle. The leaders of the movement, including Madaminbek, Shirmukhammedbek, Sher Matkul, and others, attempted to establish independent rule against the Soviets. The press movement was an expression of discontent based on socio-economic and national beliefs. The Soviets used military force to suppress this movement, resulting in the deaths of thousands of people and the destruction of villages. At the same time, the printing movement aroused national liberation sentiments among the people and laid the foundation for the future struggle with the Soviets. [9]

The revolutions of 1917 made a serious change in the history of Turkestan. On the one hand, they led to the collapse of the imperial system and the beginning of national movements, but on the other hand, they laid the foundation for the establishment of a new colonial system by the Soviets. The national movements, attempts at autonomy, and struggles for independence that began during the revolution constitute an important stage in the history of the peoples of Turkestan's quest for freedom. The impact of the October Revolution on the political situation in Turkestan is such that it initiated a new stage of political struggles in this region. National consciousness among the peoples of Turkestan has grown, and political activity has increased. As the Bolsheviks attempted to establish their power by force, a social base was formed among the local population that opposed their ideas. In

particular, peasants, religious scholars, landowners, and in some cases even ordinary artisans, dissatisfied with Bolshevik policies, took to armed struggle.

CONCLUSION. During this period, political forces were divided into two main poles. On one side were representatives of the proletariat, Russian military and communists who supported the Soviet regime, while on the other side were supporters of national independence, including Jadids, religious intellectuals, Uzbeks, Kazakhs and other Muslim ethnic groups. The establishment of Soviet rule in Turkestan, especially in the Fergana Valley, was accompanied by difficult and bloody struggles. The subsequent printing movement in this region was a sign of the continuation of the popular movement against the Bolsheviks.

In general, although the October Revolution opened the door to political freedom in Turkestan for a short time, in the long term this freedom was suppressed. National movements were suppressed, and the Soviet system of rule was forcibly introduced. This did not stop the people of Turkestan from striving for independence. On the contrary, it continued with new methods of struggle in new conditions. It was the political struggles and confrontations of 1917–1918 that prepared the ideological and political ground for the national liberation movement in Turkestan in the following years.

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